

Topographic characterization of zirconia-based ceramics by atomic force microscopy: A case study on different laser irradiations

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study is to evaluate the effects of different laser irradiations including Nd-YAG (neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet laser; Nd:Y3Al5O12), Er-YAG (erbium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet laser, erbium YAG laser), and Carbon dioxide (CO2) infrared lasers on surface topography of zirconia-based ceramics samples which were prepared by copy milling technique. Three dimensional (3D) atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were applied to investigate surface properties by extracting information via MountainsMap® Premium software which divides the surface into peaks and pits and through watershed segmentation algorithm. This method made motif analysis possible by detecting surface dimensions, curvature, volume, perimeters, shape, structure, etc.

Keywords: Atomic force microscopy, Fractal analysis, Laser irradiation, Stereometric analysis.